
MOBILE MONEY PLATFORMS AND SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION IN SELECTED (5) FIVE DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN LAGOS STATE.

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ABSTRACT

Today's banking situation demands continuous innovation in order to meet the yearnings and aspirations of the ever-demanding SMEs customers. The study examined the impact of mobile money platforms on the banks customer service delivery in Lagos Nigeria. This study specifically analysed the extent to which Point of Sale (POS) affects SMEs customer satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. And also, evaluate the effect of Electronic cards on SMEs customer satisfaction of the selected deposit money banks in Lagos State. This study adopted innovation diffusion theory and the technological acceptance model to lay a foundation for the investigation. The survey research design was chosen for this investigation through the administration of questionnaire while the regression analysis was used to determine the correlation between mobile money platforms and customer satisfaction of particular Deposit Money Banks in Lagos. Five deposit money bank branches in Lagos State served as the study's area.. Customers of the top five deposit money banks made up of First bank, UBA, GT bank, Access bank and Zenith bank (FUGAZ) made up the study's population. The result shows that mobile money platforms have positive and moderate relationship with customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State. The study concludes that mobile money platforms offers a more convenient and secure alternative to physical cash transaction. The study recommends the use of less sophisticated mobile money platforms to ease their use considering the fact that the financial literacy level of an average bank customer in Nigeria is low.

KEYWORDS: Mobile Money, Platforms, Point of Sales, Electronic Cards, SMEs

Introduction

Today's banking situation demands continuous innovation in order to meet the yearnings and aspirations of the ever-demanding SME customers. Hence, banks need to roll out new products and services quickly and effectively, using latest innovative technology (Augusto, 2012). Mobile money platform enable banks to improve their service delivery, decongest queues in the banking halls, enable SME customers withdraw cash 24/7, aid international payments and remittances, track personal banking transactions, request for online statements, or even transfer deposits to a third party account.

In order to enhance banking services, majority of banks especially the new generation banks have adopted the electronic banking services to enhance their SME customer service delivery through the advancement in information technology (Goi, 2015). Akingbola (2016) asserts that payment systems have passed through a lot of ages. Prior to 700 BC when cowries were introduced in Asia Minor, barter remained the only medium of exchange but with the introduction of coins and notes, the era of cash and payment system emerged. In AD 1000, the first bank note appeared in China. This was later followed by the use of cheque as written instructions to transfer precious metal coins from one holder to another. Other written instructions such as credit transfer, postal orders, money orders and travelers' cheques have also been introduced. The next age of payment system that followed paper instruction is electronic banking, some payments are now being automated and absolute volumes of cash transactions have declined due to the adoption of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) to the payment system especially in the developed countries.

In order to enhance the SME customer service delivery in Nigeria, banks are expected to adopt latest technologies available for electronic banking system brought about by the advancement in the information and communication technology. The increase in emerging Information Technology has made banking services become more and more automated and less paper work than in the past as averred in the Central Bank Nigeria reports and statistical bulletins, annual reports of most Nigerian banks and other literature of banking and finance (Keramati, 2017). Banks in Nigeria have realized that they would soon go out of corporate existence unless they keep with the pace at which Information Technology (IT) has redefined the creation of value and worth for their SME customers. In view of the above, this study examines the influence of cashless transactions on SME customer satisfaction: A study of (5) five selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The impact of mobile banking on the banks service delivery has not been greatly discovered in Nigeria. Few studies in Nigeria focus on mobile & internet banking adoption and more on ATM banking, this is because mobile banking is just gaining wider receivership in Nigeria (Abimbola, 2017, Abubakar, 2017, Adewale, 2019, Akinola, 2018, Echekoba & Ezu 2012, Tasmin, Abubakar & Josu, 2012). Apart from the physical challenges, economic data and indicators are not fully available and reliable. There is a great encounter in attempting to analyze the true influence of the mobile money platform on the economy of Nigeria as only little monetary and macro-economic indicators can be found with relation to the subject matter. Numerous scholars such as Alabar (2012), Hamilton, and Hewer (2012), Diwan and Singh (2010), have tried to analyze the e-banking internationally. However, it becomes clear that few studies present a comprehensive evaluation of cashless banking, implications in developing countries most disregard the economic benefits of the equation while some do

incomplete examination of its negative implications. This is often due to variable panel data for monetary and macro-economic indicators.

Researchers such as Abimbola (2017), Abubakar (2017), Adewale (2019) and Akinola (2018) conducted similar studies in Nigeria. Echekeba and Ezu (2012), in a research carried out in Nigeria, observed that 68.2% of the respondent complained about long queues in the bank, 28.9% complained of bad attitude of teller officers (cashiers) while 2.89% complained of long distance of bank locations to their home or work places. Likewise, in her 24th NCS nation conference in December 2011, CBN data shows that 51% of withdrawal done in Nigeria was through automated teller machine (ATM), while 33.6% was through over the counter (OTC) cash withdrawals and 13.6% through Cheques. Payment was also done through point of sales machine (POS) which accounted for 0.5% and web 1.3% (Akinola, 2018).

Despite the effort of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria to ensure that SME customers reap the benefits of e-banking, The Banks are still faced with complaints from SME customers as regards, malfunctioning Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), network downtime, online theft and fraud, non-availability of financial service, payment of hidden cost of electronic banking like Short Message Services (SMS), for sending alert, mandatory acquisition of ATM cards, non-acceptability of Nigerian cards for international transaction amongst others (Ovia, 2012).

In view of the above, this study will examine the effect of mobile money platform on SME customer satisfaction: A study of (5) five Domestic Important Deposit Money Banks in Lagos, acronym FUGAZ (First Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Access Bank Plc and Zenith Bank Plc)

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of mobile money platform on SME customers' satisfaction in selected (5) five Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Investigate the extent to which Point of Sale (POS) affects SME customer satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of Electronic cards on SME customer satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.

Research Questions

- i. How does Point of Sale (POS) influence SME customer satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State?
- ii. To what extent does the use of Electronic cards influence SME customer satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and strengthen the analysis.

Hypothesis one

H₀: Point of Sale (POS) does not significantly affect SME customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State

Hypothesis two

H0: Electronic cards do not significantly affect SME customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.

Concept of Mobile Banking

This is a form of E-Banking that involves using mobile phones to carry out banking transactions. This is a system that offers information to SME customers and other bank services. Some of the services which are provided through mobile banking include account balance inquiry, payment of bills, short message service (SMS). It enables transactions to be done anywhere in the world and at the SME customer's convenience. This banking is also called 'motion banking'. It allows the SME customer to perform banking transactions at any time as long as a mobile phone is present (Ayodele, 2015).

Olayemi (2002) defines mobile-phone banking as a service provided by a financial institution which allows its SME customers, micro, small and medium scale enterprises, persons and other business ventures to perform transactions over the mobile telephone. He further states that it enables the SME customer to check his/her account balances, give instruction for bill payment, transfer money between accounts in the same bank and other banks, make payment for goods purchased or services rendered. Mobile banking (also known as M-banking) is a term used for performing balance checks, account transactions, payments, credit applications and other banking transactions through a mobile device such as mobile phones or personal digital assistant (PDA). According to Worku, Tilahun and Tafa (2016), the earliest mobile banking services were offered over SMS, a service known as SMS banking. Mobile banking is in use in many parts of the world with little or no infrastructure, especially remote rural areas.

Concerning the effect of mobile banking (MB) on MSMEs sector operations, the benefits are numerous. Personal mobile phone banking provides quality and efficient banking services through the combination of self-services, voice system and call center representatives (Martila and Martila, 2005). They listed some benefits of personal mobile-phone banking services to MSMEs to include balance checks, account transactions, payments, credit applications and other formal banking transactions which have brought so much efficiency in business operations. As a form of electronic banking, mobile phone banking prevents transaction friction that often occurs during the use of physical cash in transactions (Ajayi, 2014). Therefore, cashless banking is that banking system which aims at reducing, but not eliminating totally, the volume of physical cash in circulation. In other words, it is a combination of e-banking and cash-based system (Ajayi, 2014).

Concept of Point of Sale (POS)

Central Bank of Nigeria introduced Point of sale and gave the guidelines in 2011 with maximum service commission of 1.25% or a maximum of NGN2000 and limiting the role of connecting and maintaining POS devices only to licensed Payment Terminal Service Providers (PTSPs). These POS terminals serve like the Automatic Teller Machines (ATM) across commercial points in the country. At the completion of a transaction and the value ascertained, the amount is entered into a POS terminal into which the electronic card has been slotted. The cash equivalent of the amount will be automatically transferred from the payer's account into the account of the payee's account. In Nigeria today, private enterprise, religious bodies, educational institutions and other service providers such as hotels, transport firms etc. have embraced the POS option in their transactions.

This is a form of e-payment that handles balance inquiry, payment for goods and service, electronic fund transfer at a specific point of sale. The device allows SME customers to make payment for goods and services purchased without the physical use of cash. At POS terminals, when a SME customer slots in his card into the POS, he inputs his details and in the case of payment for goods or services, his account is debited at that point resulting in a transfer of funds to the service provider's account.

Electronic Cards System

These are cards that contain integrated circuits which can process data and are used for conducting financial obligations. Electronic cards could be debit or credit cards. The difference between debit and credit cards is; debit cards are used for payment of purchases made and the money comes from the SME customer's account directly. On the other hand, payment for goods or service using the credit card is based on borrowing. The most preferred cards used by Nigerians are the master and visa cards.

Concept of Customer Satisfaction

According to Wright and Ralson (2012), customer satisfaction is the culmination of perception, assessment, and emotional responses to the experience of using a product or service. To put it another way, Wright and Ralson go on to describe customer satisfaction as the outcome of a cognitive and affective evaluation in which the perceived performance is actually compared to a comparison standard. An organization's client base, usage of a more volatile customer mix, and reputation can all grow with increased customer satisfaction (Alabar, 2012). Ikechukwu (2010) states that the phrase "customer satisfaction," which is often used in marketing, refers to how well a company's goods and services meet or exceed the expectations of its clients. Customer happiness, he said, is determined by the quantity or proportion percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals.

According to Nwaze (2019), satisfaction is the consumer's assessment that a product has delivered or is now delivering a pleasurable degree of consumption-related fulfillment. It is a judgment that follows a consuming experience. Customers experience the product performance during consumption and assess how well it meets their expectations. This comparison is then used to produce satisfaction evaluations. If the performance meets or exceeds expectations, the resultant judgment is labeled as positive disconfirmation; otherwise, it is labeled as simple confirmation. Simply said, consumers assess a product's performance by drawing comparisons between their expectations and what they think they actually received. In the corporate world, customer satisfaction is seen as a critical performance measure and is frequently included in a balanced scorecard. In a cutthroat industry where companies generally ask customers whether their product or service has met or exceeded expectations. Thus, expectations are a key factor behind satisfaction. When consumers have high expectations and the reality falls they will be disappointed and will likely rate their experience as less than satisfying.

The influence of e-banking on SME customer satisfaction

According to Saha and Zhao (2015), customer satisfaction is defined as a collection of outcome of perception, evaluation and psychological reactions to the consumption experience with a product/service. In other words, Saha and Zhao further define customer satisfaction as a result of a cognitive and affective evaluation where some comparison standard is compared to the actually perceived performance. Customer's satisfaction holds the potential for increasing an organization's customer base, increase the use of more volatile customer mix

and increase the firm's reputation (Alabar, 2012). Consequently, obtaining competitive advantage is secured through intelligent identification and satisfaction of customer's needs better and sooner than competitors and sustenance of customer's satisfaction through better products/services. Technology is then essential in providing faster and more efficient services to customers. Technology acquisition must be based on actual needs and the proven ability to deliver customer – friendly solutions (Alabar, 2012). Howcroft, Hamilton, and Hewer (2012) agree that e-banking services have significant effect on customer satisfaction. Diwan and Singh (2010) argue that the online banking extends the relationship with the customers through providing financial services right into the home or office of customers. Ovia (2012) finds that electronic banking usage has a considerable effect on customer satisfaction among the electronic banking users, while it has a negative impact on non-users. It was concluded that customer care and customer retention should be taken into consideration, because the convenient, easy and fast banking services is associated with the human and technology based delivery processes so that they are linked with the customers' perceptions of how these bank services are delivered to them. Chakrabarti and Kardile (2012) who contend that higher levels of website usability might lead to higher levels of consumer's affective commitment to the website as well a direct, positive and significant relationship between satisfaction in previous interactions and the consumer's commitment to a financial services website

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted innovation diffusion theory and the technological acceptance model.

Innovation Diffusion Theory

Innovation diffusion theory was developed by Roger in 1983. This theory explains individuals' intention to adopt a technology as a modality to perform a traditional activity. The critical factors that determine the adoption of an innovation at the general level are the following thus the assumptions: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability. It is concerned with the manner in which a new technological idea, artefact or technique, or a new use of an old one, migrates from creation to use (Kim, 2016). According to innovation diffusion theory, technological innovation is communicated through particular channels, over time, among the members of a social system.

The stages through which a technological innovation passes are: knowledge (exposure to its existence, and understanding of its functions); persuasion (the forming of a favorable attitude to it); decision (commitment to its adoption); implementation (putting it to use); and confirmation (reinforcement based on positive outcomes from it). The important assumptions of the theory include: i) Relative advantage (the degree to which it is perceived to be better than what it supersedes); ii) Compatibility (consistency with existing values, past experiences and needs); iii) Complexity (difficulty of understanding and use); iv) Trialability (the degree to which it can be experimented with on a limited basis); v) observability (the visibility of its results). Different adopter categories are identified as: innovators (venturesome); early adopters (respectable); early majority (deliberate); iv) Late majority (sceptical); Earlier adopting individuals tend not to be different in age, but to have more years of education, higher social status and upward social mobility, be in larger organizations, have greater empathy, less dogmatism, a greater ability to deal with abstractions, greater rationality, greater intelligence, a greater ability to cope with uncertainty and risk, higher aspirations, more contact with other people, greater exposure to both mass media and interpersonal communications channels and engage in more active information seeking (Kim, 2016). Important roles in the innovation process include: opinion leaders (who have relatively frequent informal influence over the behaviour of others); change agents (who positively

influence innovation decisions, by mediating between the change agency and the relevant social system); change aides (who complement the change agent, by having more intensive contact with clients, and who have less competence credibility but more correctly or trustworthiness credibility).

The change agent functions are: to develop a need for change on the part of the client; to establish an information-exchange relationship; to diagnose the client problems; to create intent to change in the client; to translate this intent into action; to stabilize adoption and prevent discontinuance; and to shift the client from reliance on the change agent to self-reliance (Dennis, 2011). The relevance of the theory to the study is that it stresses that technological innovation which is communicated through particular channels (internet, ATM, POS), over time has ensure the efficiency and effectiveness in the banking sector, thus improve the performance of banks in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Amin, Onyeukwu and Osuagwu (2018) investigated on E – banking, service quality and customer satisfaction in selected Nigerian banks. This study examined the relationship between the quality of service and customer satisfaction in the e-banking era. A sample of 398 respondents was selected, out of the total number of 66,895 customer population. Structured questionnaires and interview were used in collecting the data. Descriptive statistics was adopted in analyzing the data from the respondents. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between quality of service and customer satisfaction. The study concluded that E-banking has a positive impact on the quality of service in the Nigerian banking sector, but not on customer satisfaction. The study recommended that staff training and development should be enhanced in the banking industry in order to render quality and timely services to their customers.

Additionally, these issues may have an impact on sales and profitability when these ratings decline. When a company has devoted following, it Simon and Senaji (2016) looked into how customer satisfaction was affected by electronic banking in a few Kenyan commercial banks. Determining the relationship between electronic banking and customer satisfaction at Nairobi Town's first-tier banks was the study's main goal. Diffusion innovation theory and contrast theory served as the study's main pillars. A descriptive survey research design was used in the study. 262,511 clients were the target population, and they were selected from five of the top banks in the Nairobi CBD. To choose a sample size of 225 respondents, the stratified sampling technique was applied. Participants' responses to standardized questionnaires were used to gather primary data.

Onobrakpeya and Mac-Attama (2017) investigated on improving customer satisfaction through digital marketing in the Nigerian deposit money banks. The objective of the study was to ascertain the effect of digital marketing on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian deposits money banks. The study made use of a sample of 214 employees from some selected banks in Warri Metropolis in Delta State, Nigeria. Cross sectional survey research design method was adopted, and the statistical techniques used comprised of simple percentage, correlation and multiple regression analysis. Findings showed that e-mail marketing have the highest significant positive effect on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian deposit money banks. The implication is that customers appreciate regular communication via e-mail because it brings value and satisfaction to them. The study concluded that companies whose website have quality contents are ranked higher in search engine results and are better positioned in achieving superior performance by way of customer satisfaction. The study recommended that a strategy should be put in place to integrate mobile marketing with other

digital marketing media during its implementation because it is difficult to separate customers from their mobile devices and gadget.

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Obisesan, Adeleke & Ogunsanwo (2019) study investigated the effect of CBN's cashless policy on the development of financial sector in Nigeria. The study was borne out to establish whether cashless policy have been accepted by the Nigerian citizens and to evaluate its influence on financial sector. The study was limited to five deposit money banks in Ekiti State, namely (First bank, Zenith bank, Diamond bank, Access bank and UBA; selected using simple random sampling technique. 135 questionnaire were distributed and retrieved from the members of staff of the deposit money banks.

The result of the tests of hypotheses revealed that: cashless policy tool, implementation of cashless policy and awareness of cashless policy affect the development of financial sector in Nigeria; cashless policy tool contributed significantly to the development of financial sector Adedokun (2017), evaluated the effect of cashless banking on the financial performance of small and medium

In their 2017 study, Uchechukwu, Chubuzor, Donatus, and Gloria evaluated the empirical analysis of the impact of the cashless policy on the banking industry's performance in Nigeria from 2008 to 2015. The study used earnings per share (EPS), return on equity (ROE), and return on asset (ROA) as metrics for evaluating bank performance. The study used the parametric statistical pooled variance/paired sample t-test model to evaluate the hypothesis. The study's conclusions indicated that while banks' earnings per share have increased, the Central Bank of Nigeria's 2012 implementation of the cashless policy did not improve the banks' returns on equity or assets. The study concluded that, in light of its findings, the cashless strategy is not one that aims to improve bank performance inscale enterprises in Zaria Metropolis. The study is cross sectional in nature and collected data using self-administered questionnaire to 120 respondents. The study employed multiple regression and found that mobile banking and Point of Sales (POS) machine services have significant positive effect on the financial performance of SMEs. The study noted that the cashless policy is not a policy targeted towards enhancing bank performance in terms of profitability.

In 2016, Taiwo, Ayo, Afieroho, and Agwu investigated the impact of the cashless policy on the Nigerian financial system. With the use of the questionnaire, which was given at random to 120 respondents from First Bank, Zenith Bank, and United Bank for Africa, the study used primary data. The information gathered included the actions taken by the CBN and these banks in relation to the implementation of the cashless policy from 2012 to the present. The banks were chosen on the basis of their overall assets.

Adu (2016) looked into the benefits to the economy and stakeholders of the cashless policy, its origins in Lagos, methods of payments (manually and electronically), its positive and negative effects, and its effects on the policy's overall impact. The Nigerian government was given recommendations on how to mitigate some of the policy's drawbacks and enhance its execution.

Ugwueze & Nwezeaku (2016), studied E-banking and Commercial Bank Performance in Nigeria: A Cointegration and Causality Approach. Engle-Granger cointegration model was used to analyse data for the sample period January 2009 to December 2013. The results showed that POS is not cointegrated with both the savings and time deposits but are cointegrated with demand deposits.

Methodology

The survey research design was chosen for this investigation. The study employed a survey research design in an effort to characterize and elucidate the study's conditions through the administration of questionnaires to determine the correlation between the cashless policy and customer satisfaction of particular Deposit Money Banks in Lagos. To get the opinions of the number of respondents, this design uses a sample. This type of study strategy examines data obtained from a subset or proportion of the population. The five chosen Deposit Money Bank branches in Lagos State served as the study's subject area. Customers of the top five Deposit Money Banks (FUGAZ) branches made up the study's population.

Model Specification

The independent variable for the study which is cashless policy was measured by Debit and Credit Card Payment System (DCPS) E-Cash System (ECS), Automated Teller Machine Services (ATMS), Mobile phones transfers (MPT).

On the other hand, Customer satisfaction is the dependent variable. Mathematically, CS is a function of cashless policy.

$$Y = f(X_i)$$

Y = Dependent variable = Customer Satisfaction (CS)

X = Independent variable = Mobile money platforms (MMP)

$$CS = f(MMP)$$

Since MMP = POS, ECs,

Therefore, CS = $f(POS, ECS)$.

$$Y = X_i$$

$$X_i = X_1, X_2,$$

Where

Y = Customer Satisfaction (CS)

X = Mobile money platforms (MMP)

The indicators of Mobile money platforms (MMP) (X) are;

X₁ = Point of Sale (POS)

$X_2 = \text{E-Cash System (ECS)}$

$CS = a_0 + \beta_1 \text{ POS} + \beta_2 \text{ ECS} + e_i \dots\dots\dots \text{Model}$

$a_0 =$ intercept on the Y axis

$\beta_i =$ Rate of change in customer satisfaction due to adoption of Mobile money platforms

$e_i =$ Error term

Summary of multiple regression analysis for the effect of mobile money platforms on customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State

Model	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	ANOVA Sig.	F(df)
(Constant)	0.43	4.51	0.00	0.68	0.462	0.459	0.000	149.27 (4,241)
E-cash system	0.26	7.65	0.00					
Point of Sales	0.29	8.81	0.00					

Source: Computed by the Researcher (2024)

The result shows that mobile money platforms have positive and moderately average relationship with customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State ($R = 0.68$, $p=0.000$). The adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj R^2) of 0.459 showed that cashless policy practices explained 45.9% of the variation in customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State while the remaining 54.1% variation in customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos; is explained by other exogenous variable different from those considered in this study.

The results of regression coefficients for mobile money platforms in relation to customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State revealed that at 95% confidence level, E-cash system ($\beta = 0.26$, $p= 0.000$), Point of Sales ($\beta = 0.29$, $p= 0.000$), were statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05 and the t-values greater than 1.96.

Based on the coefficients of regression in the table above, the regression model is restated as follows:

$$CS = 0.43 + 0.26 \text{ ECS} + 0.29 \text{ POS} \dots\dots\dots \text{Eq.}$$

According to the regression equation above, considering all factors, a unit change in E-cash system will also lead to a 0.26 increase in customer satisfaction given that all other factors are considered while the results also revealed that a unit change in Point of Sales will lead to a 0.29 increase in customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State given that all other factors are considered.

Conclusion

The mobile money platforms offer a more convenient and secure alternative to physical cash. The benefits are numerous, from faster transactions to reduced costs and risks associated with physical currency, such as theft and fraud. In the past, a cashless society was not an entirely new concept. . Electronic fund transfers, mobile payment apps, and digital wallets are now part of our everyday lives, and Nigeria is no exception. With the use of mobile money platforms, the country is on a path to becoming a cashless or cash-lite economy, and this presents an unprecedented opportunity for digital payment providers.

Recommendations

The study recommends the use of less sophisticated mobile money platforms to ease their use considering the fact that the financial literacy level of an average bank customer in Nigeria is low.

Also, the complexity of web-enabled banking applications would reduce corruption, fight terrorism, build an environment of honesty and transparent transaction regime as almost all transaction carried out leaves a trail between the initiator and the beneficiary real time.

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